

MODERN METHODS AND APPROACHES OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *This article tells us about need of learning English language. For This aim is necessary to use different methods and approaches to teaching of English language. Main methods of teaching English are considered.*

Key words: *method, approach, content, communication, motivation, language.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И ПОДХОДЫ К ПРЕПОДАВАНИЮ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: *В статье говорится о необходимости изучения английского языка. Для этого нужно использовать разнообразные методики и подходы к преподаванию английского языка. Рассматриваются основные методики преподавания английского.*

Ключевые слова: *метод, подход, содержание, коммуникация, мотивация, язык.*

With the formation of new means of communication, "the world, as the English say, is getting smaller," which means there is a need to learn languages, helping us find a common language with foreigners when traveling, get a new position, find friends from all over the world, or even arrange a personal life. No wonder more and more people want to know him. The more people want to study it, the more techniques appear. What is the methodology and why it is so important to choose the right one.

In other words, the methodology includes the principles and means of teaching, methods of learning a foreign language. But as already noted, with the emergence of a huge number of people willing to learn a foreign language, the number of methods has

also increased. Before to immerse yourself in learning a language, you need to choose a suitable option for yourself. Let's consider the main known methods of teaching English. Task based learning. The approach of the late 80s, popularity wandered in the mid-2000s. The theory was outlined by Peter Shen, Rod Ellis, Jane Willis. Basic principles: TBL is a branch of the communicative method, where students perform thematic tasks; the use of materials and exercises that students perform in life; the main thing is to complete the task (rent a car, conduct an interview) using the language structures that are in the student's everyday life; the task includes: Task > Planning > Report (1996, Jane Willis). Students explain how they performed the task and what goals they achieved. For example, developing a presentation for the whole group is a difference from the traditional PPP (presentation, practice, production) method. CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning). It has been known since 1994, but it has gained popularity since the middle of 2000. The term was introduced by David Marsh. The main principles: the remaining subjects are studied with the help of the English language, i.e. we learn both the language and the content. We acquire knowledge and learn the language; the content must be understandable and accompanied by visual supports (pictures, graphs, diagrams); all types of speech activity are integrated, but the language does not adapt depending on the level. Problems: lack of material and qualified teachers. Dogme ELT. The approach began to gain popularity in 2001. The methodology was formulated by Scott Thornberry. Main methods: "freedom" from books and notes: important language structures are not prepared by the teacher in advance, but "pop up" in the educational process. At the same time, the lesson can be completely unpredictable for the teacher; the content is created by students (monologues, videos and audio recordings); what happens in the lesson, including materials, acquires an indirect relation to the life of students. Disadvantages: it requires flexibility from the teacher, the ability to quickly rebuild and a lot of experience. It is not suitable for preparation for specialized courses, for example, tests, and use for preparatory levels.

Flipped classroom. 2007, the founders are considered to be Jonathan Begman and Aaron Sens. Later, this trend began to be used in teaching English. The main principles: the task is given to students to work out before the lesson (for example, a video lecture on grammar), time is not spent on theory analysis during the lesson itself, all attention is paid to discussion and productive practice; students study at a pace suitable for them and come to the lesson prepared; thanks to the independent work of students, teachers cover more material. Disadvantages: Suitable for motivated students of above average level. It is a lecture-style training, while students receive information passively. They are not involved in the analysis of the topic, guided discovery is not used here.

Audiolingual Method. Often the audiolingual approach is also called the Army method. It is based on the postulate of behaviorism that it is possible and necessary to study and assimilate a variety of things with the help of continuous repetition. The method involves oral presentation of the material and repeated repetition of different lexical and grammatical structures under the guidance of a teacher.

Direct Method. The method appeared in the 1900s in Germany and France for training military communication in a foreign language. It is also also called Natural Method (Natural method). It is similar to the audio-lingual approach, involves repeated repetition and development of various structures.

The main difference in language learning is inductive, that is, the teacher does not explain the rule to the students, but on the contrary, helps them to understand and deduce it on the basis of language material. It is also worth noting that both in the audio-lingual and in the direct method, the teacher uses exclusively the language being studied; the native language is not allowed.

Suggestopedia (Suggestopedia). Despite the fact that this method is often regarded as pseudoscientific, for some time it was very widely known. This method is based on the student's confidence that the principle will work; light trance technologies are used. Great attention is focused on ensuring that the student does not experience the slightest stress during the lesson. The use of music is also widely used in the method.

Total Physical Response. The approach is based on the principle of "practice by studying". It works great with younger students, schoolchildren. In the lessons, the execution of commands and instructions is practiced. Thus, the student remembers the simplest replicas, which eventually become quite difficult.

The Silent Way (Silent approach). In this approach, the emphasis is on the independence of students: the teacher, as the name of the method implies, does not actually speak (for example, does not give detailed and lengthy explanations of grammar). He plays the role of an assistant who guides the students. Phonetics is of great importance – it takes a lot of time at each lesson. The studied vocabulary and grammar are also systematically repeated. Often, students do not even write formal tests on the studied material; instead, the teacher evaluates their progress from lesson to lesson. **The Lexical Approach.** The main goal is to master the vocabulary. Initially, a list of very frequently used words and lexical constructions is determined, and the study takes place little by little, from simple to complex. Much less attention is paid to grammar than in other methods.

This article describes only some common methods and approaches in modern methods of teaching English. They will not always suit you: you can periodically use some elements in the classroom, for example, conduct two classes a month using the

method Dogme Elt, CLIL or Flipped classroom. The use of intensive methods of teaching foreign languages is quite an interesting and effective education option. Each approach has both advantages and disadvantages. The main goal of a foreign language teacher is to be able to find an appropriate method for his contingent of students. To choose an acceptable method, the teacher needs to take into account the following: the student must feel comfortable and free, be motivated to learn and use a foreign language; take initiative, be an active participant in the educational process; understand that learning a foreign language depends more on himself, on his interest; the teacher needs to stimulate speech, cognitive and creative abilities of the student; there should be various forms of activity in the classroom (individual, group), stimulating the activity, independence and creativity of students.

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